

Mapping opportunities for a neighborhood-scale sharing economy: A geospatial methodological framework focused on household products

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ABSTRACT

The sharing economy (SE) could promote environmental sustainability, though its outcomes often depend on the SE's ability to reduce product consumption and transportation impacts. In this study, we develop a methodological framework to identify where the implementation of sharing can contribute to sustainability by reducing both aspects. The framework involves neighborhood-level extrapolation of consumption and user attitudes, as well as spatial analyses of existing sharing initiatives. Through these steps, we can compare supply and demand of 6 sharing activities (i.e., reparation, buying and selling second-hand, loaning to and from private individuals, and renting) and 7 product groups (clothes, tools, furniture, electronics, and children-, hobby- and kitchen equipment), and evaluate the level of pedestrian accessibility and centrality in different neighborhoods. The viability of the methodological framework is demonstrated by using the case city of Gothenburg, Sweden, focusing on mediated and locally accessible sharing. Based on a non-comprehensive data sample, the results show consistent spatial patterns in product consumption; more distinct patterns regarding attitudes and the presence of initiatives; and unfulfilled sharing demands for tools, furniture, and various types of equipment. Additionally, product-based unfulfilled demands were more prevalent in the outer city neighborhoods, whereas sharing activity-based unfulfilled demands increased toward the inner city. Opportunities for sustainable sharing were identified for locations with medium-high levels of centrality. Future research implies improving the results for Gothenburg with representative data, and the development of the method to accommodate other types of sustainable sharing.

1. Introduction

In light of increasing household consumption rates and their adverse environmental effects at the urban level (Di Donato et al., 2015; Shittu, 2020), the sharing economy (SE) offers a possibility to transition towards more sustainable consumption patterns. While the precise meaning of the SE is contested, definitions often involve the redistribution of products, services, and spaces. The SE can encompass various activities involving formal or informal, permanent or temporary exchanges, and through models like peer-to-peer (P2P), mediated business-to-consumer (B2C), and mediated peer-to-peer sharing (P2B2P). Further, mediated forms can manifest physically or digitally (Botsman and Rogers, 2010; Frenken and Schor, 2017; Puschmann and Alt, 2016) with the involvement of sharing initiatives (SIs). Users of the

SE, whether providers or consumers, could contribute to reducing individual purchases of newly manufactured products and to more efficient use of resources already existing in cities (European Commission, 2016).

However, it is still uncertain to what extent the SE can fulfill its sustainability potential (Codagnone and Martens, 2016). Several studies have highlighted factors that could affect the SE's outcomes in comparison to conventional purchases, including the types of assets and sharing activities (Curtis and Lehner, 2019; Meshulam et al., 2024), the population's interest levels and adoption rates (Jiménez Encarnación et al., 2024), and the SE's actual ability to reduce product purchases (Curtis and Mont, 2020; Faraji et al., 2024). While it is often assumed that sharing replaces new product purchases, this is not always the case (Ribera Jemio et al., 2024). For instance, electronic products are more

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likely to be replaced (Dhanorkar, 2019), whereas products like clothing may not be. Additionally, economic gains from sharing can lead to increased consumption of other goods, known as rebound effects (Frenken and Schor, 2017). Furthermore, the intensified use of shared assets can result in higher impacts from cleaning, maintenance, and more frequent replacements due to shorter lifecycles (Zamani et al., 2017).

In addition to these factors, transportation impacts are consistently identified as crucial, particularly for activities such as renting and loaning (Johnson and Plepys, 2021). The distance between providers and consumers, as well as the mode of transportation used to procure shared products, could make sharing more environmentally impactful than purchasing new products, even when consumption is reduced. Increased user trips for sharing can also negate the benefits of non-consumption, especially for products with low production and use-phase impacts (e.g., t-shirts, sports equipment) or when using certain transportation modes (Fani and Bandinelli, 2023; Martin et al., 2019; Zamani et al., 2017). So, while SIs often claim to be more environmentally sustainable than linear consumption (Geissinger et al., 2019), user behavior regarding product replacement and transportation is essential for the outcome (Curtis and Mont, 2020).

The impacts of transportation have been studied for both digital and physical sharing, including individual transportation modes and logistic services (Behrend, 2020; Martin et al., 2021; Zamani et al., 2017). Nonetheless, transportation distances in these studies are often assumed, which could ultimately impact the amounts and types of resulting environmental effects. In turn, these assumptions may be based on a lack of data on the geospatial aspects of the sharing transaction. The geospatial dimension of sharing involves the location of product peer-providers or SIs that facilitate sharing transactions (i.e., supply); the location of SE consumers (i.e., demand); and the distances involved in the sharing transaction. Although sharing can lead to lower environmental impacts when involving short distances and/or low-emitting transportation modes (Demailly and Novel, 2014; Frenken and Schor, 2017), the spatial dimensions of sharing have not been sufficiently investigated (Sánchez-Vergara et al., 2021).

Besides their influence on the resulting impacts, geospatial aspects can affect users' interest and participation in sharing. For example, in P2P mobility and accommodation sharing, the location of the supply can affect its price and, consequently, user engagement (Boros et al., 2018). Location characteristics can also affect which products and platform models are more attractive for sharing. Affolderbach and de Chardon (2021) found that in central city areas, P2P and B2C sharing of tangible goods is more abundant, as a high population density implies a richer offer of products. In Sweden, the optimal location for SIs relied on area characteristics (e.g., areas with gardens increased interest in sharing gardening equipment, Hunka and Habibi, 2023). Similarly, Herold and Prokop (2023) and Ala-Mantila et al. (2017) found differing levels of participation in product sharing between urban and rural areas, as urban areas represent less effort to reach providers and more SI variety. Finally, proximity to SIs could be a primary motivator for non-sharers to start engaging in the SE (Öhrwall, 2021; Skjelvik et al., 2017).

Thus, the relationship between transportation modes, location, shared products, and sharing activities is relevant, as these could determine interest, participation, and the types of environmental impacts that might be mitigated. Until now, the geospatial aspects of sharing have been studied with high granularity for mobility (Du et al., 2019; Thebault-Spieker et al., 2017) and space (i.e., accommodation and co-working spaces, Coll-Martínez and Méndez-Ortega, 2023; Mariotti et al., 2017). These studies consider the exact location of SIs and the location characteristics, but a similar level of detail has not been observed in studies of household product sharing. For household products, most studies only consider whether "location", as a general concept, determines interest in SIs (Hunka and Habibi, 2023; Kireeva et al., 2021; Vaskelainen and Piscicelli, 2018), or how assumed distances between consumers and providers (both physical SIs and online P2B2P

sharers) affect environmental outcomes (Blocket AB, 2013; Martin et al., 2021; Martin et al., 2019).

As such, we identify a gap for high-granularity studies that consider the geospatial dimension of household product consumption and sharing. This type of knowledge can be valuable for urban governance and planning. So far, planning practices for sustainability have prioritized housing, transportation, and waste flows but have neglected the consumption of material goods (Hult and Bradley, 2017). Yet, urban governance and planning are crucial for fulfilling the SE's potential for sustainable consumption, especially by adapting strategies to different local conditions (Codagnone and Martens, 2016; Henry et al., 2021). An increased understanding of household consumption and sharing at the urban level could enable evidence-based governance and planning, for example, by targeting areas with high product consumption (Meshulam et al., 2024; Shittu, 2020). Besides that, the SE also presents opportunities for fostering entrepreneurship and civic involvement (European Commission, 2016). Unfortunately, initiatives with environmental motives often fail to thrive (Geissinger et al., 2019), so understanding how the demand for sustainable sharing manifests in different locations could indicate where different types of SIs have an increased chance of succeeding.

This study, therefore, aims to develop a novel methodological framework to explore the geospatial dimensions of sharing at the city and neighborhood levels. The viability of the methodological framework is exemplified through the research question, "How does the spatial distribution of supply and demand of sharing throughout the city reveal areas with untapped opportunities?", taking the city of Gothenburg, Sweden, as a case. While the framework could be useful for a wide array of sharing forms, we showcase its applicability through studying physical initiatives in B2C and P2B2P formats, sharing of tangible and durable household products, and transactions within walking and biking distances (see further details about the scope in Section 3.2).

The article is structured as follows: Chapter 2 provides the theoretical background for the methodological choices. Chapter 3 details the framework steps. Chapter 4 showcases and verifies the types of results that can be obtained by utilizing the framework. Chapter 5 discusses the framework's advances, limitations, and implications. Chapter 6 presents the final remarks.

2. Theory

2.1. Sharing for environmental sustainability

The sharing economy is an umbrella construct initially driven by the work of Botsman and Rogers (2010) on "collaborative consumption". These authors included activities where asset ownership is transferred (e.g., gifting, swapping) or maintained (e.g., lending and borrowing); for free (e.g., sharing), or for a fee (e.g., renting, second-hand purchasing). Other broad conceptualizations focus on access to underutilized assets (Acquier et al., 2017) and on sustainable consumption SE platforms, also called sharing initiatives (SIs), which provide the assets or coordinate transactions between peer providers and consumers (Cohen and Muñoz, 2016). More restrictive definitions of the SE focus on specific criteria – for example, delimiting the SE to non-commercial access rather than monetized transfers (Belk, 2014), or to digitally mediated P2P exchanges (Curtis and Lehner, 2019).

SE activities have an intuitive association with environmental sustainability, as the potential reduction of individual product purchases is linked to a more efficient use of materials (Kalmykova et al., 2018), a decrease in production and raw material extraction (Ala-Mantila et al., 2017); less water, energy use, and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Cheng, 2016), and reduced waste amounts (Puschmann and Alt, 2016). Therefore, authors like Meshulam et al. (2024) emphasize targeting consumers with environmentally intensive consumption patterns to encourage them to share more. Nonetheless, the idea of a sustainable SE is complex, and influenced by various factors (Codagnone and Martens,

2016; Demailly and Novel, 2014; Frenken and Schor, 2017). Some of the factors that can affect the outcome of sharing are reviewed below:

As stated, whether the SE can be more sustainable than purchasing new products depends on its capacity to reduce net consumption. However, increased consumption can occur either upstream or downstream of the sharing transaction. For example, an SI could make an excessive number of purchases to provide products, as was seen with bike-sharing SIs in China (Taylor, 2018) or peer providers could make purchases solely to rent out to consumers and not for personal use. These cases create a new product stock and artificial idling rather than harnessing the capacity of existing underutilized assets (Curtis and Lehner, 2019; Heinrichs, 2013; Meshulam et al., 2024). Likewise, if sharing is not replacing a purchase, rather creating a new need, the sharing transaction can increase environmental effects. The replacement of consumption might be especially relevant for products with higher environmental impacts in the production stage, such as electronics (Johnson and Plepys, 2021; Kouloumpis et al., 2023). Downstream, rebound effects occur if the money saved (i.e., consumer) or generated (i.e., provider) through sharing, is utilized in other resource or GHG-intensive purchases.

Another factor closely related to the sustainability potential of the SE is which asset is being shared. Academics agree that sharing goods, specifically tangible assets, could lead to better environmental outcomes than accommodation and mobility (Curtis and Lehner, 2019; Meshulam et al., 2024). Further, the product type may be more significant than the platform model used to share it (Laukkanen and Tura, 2020). A drawback for certain tangible products, especially in temporary transactions, is the need for cleaning and repair which might represent additional impacts (Meshulam et al., 2024).

In addition, several studies explore the importance of transportation for both digital and physical sharing practices, particularly in the context of temporary transactions. Different modes of transferring products from providers to consumers have been studied, including the use of cars, public transportation, biking, walking, postal services, shared storage boxes, and delivery services. Results indicate that the distance traveled and mode of transportation used for sharing may lead to higher GHG emissions and lower resource efficiency (Martin et al., 2019, 2021). This applies to logistics trips in B2P models (Meshulam et al., 2024; Zamani et al., 2017), but also to trips taken by SE users. Accordingly, Zamani et al. (2017) conceptualize low-impact sharers as those who walk, bike, or take the bus for relatively short distances to retrieve products. Martin et al. (2021) recommend that tool rental SIs be located close to both consumers and providers, while Martin et al. (2019) propose the use of postal services and the installation of sharing boxes within apartment buildings. User behavior also plays a role, as transport impacts can be minimized by combining sharing trips with other tasks as shopping and errands (Johnson and Plepys, 2021). Low transportation impacts are especially relevant for sharing that substitutes consumption, as repeated trips to access a product might offset the impacts of non-consumption (Skjelvik et al., 2017).

Otherwise, the relationship between product ownership and the sustainability of the SE is less straightforward. While Curtis and Lehner (2019) and Faraji et al. (2024) emphasize that sustainable sharing provides access (e.g., loaning) rather than transfers ownership (i.e., buying second-hand), Laukkanen and Tura (2020) and Zamani et al. (2017) found that access-based sharing can be linked to rebound effects and increased transport impacts to procure and return items. Faraji et al. (2024) posit that ownership transfer may not provide environmental benefits but might still extend the lifetime of goods, which other authors consider essential in leveraging sustainability (Curtis and Mont, 2020; Zamani et al., 2017). Additionally, the discussion of ownership structure typically relates to the platform model used. Curtis and Lehner (2019) and Curtis and Mont (2020) highlight P2B2P temporary transactions for improved sustainability, whereas Parguel et al. (2017) and Meshulam et al. (2024) link P2P with overconsumption and negative outcomes.

Similarly, the infrastructure types of sharing, namely digital (e.g.,

apps, websites) and physical (e.g., brick-and-mortar shops, sharing boxes), have different implications for environmental sustainability. A large part of the SE literature only includes digital forms; thus, definitions of sustainable sharing (e.g., Curtis and Mont, 2020) focus on digital sharing due to its adherence to more traditional views of the SE. Quantitative studies comparing the sustainability potential of both digital and physical sharing with the purchase of new products are scarce; among these, the works by Behrend (2020) and Zamani et al. (2017). Both identify digital sharing as the most beneficial option, but the results are mostly tied to assumed shorter transportation distances for online sharing. Additionally, the impacts of the digital and physical infrastructures are often excluded from assessments, with some exceptions for sharing lockers and boxes (Martin et al., 2019, 2021).

To support the conceptualization of the methodological framework, we adopt a simplified definition of environmentally sustainable sharing. We base the framework on sharing that 1) reduces net consumption, 2) minimizes transportation impacts, and 3) facilitates tangible goods, and draw no limitations regarding platform models, sharing activities, ownership structures, or infrastructure types. Due to data availability, the methodological framework is only showcased through the study of mediated physical sharing at walking and biking distances.

2.2. Consumption and sharing from a theoretical perspective

In this section, we depart from the main theoretical trends in sustainable consumption and expand on research regarding user participation in the SE. The theory in this section supports the choice of variables in the framework, and our discussion (see section 5.3.).

2.2.1. Main theories within consumption

Several theories from the economic, management, and psychology fields have been applied to study consumption and sharing (Camacho-Otero et al., 2018; Hossain, 2020; Zoli and Congiu, 2024). These theories have not only driven understanding of consumer decisions but also provided insights on how to drive behavioral change.

Initially, economic theories explained consumption through rational choice models, where individuals base their decisions on cost-benefit analyses (Jackson, 2005). Challenging these models, behavioral economists demonstrated that human behavior is also influenced by cognitive biases and mental shortcuts (Tversky and Kahneman, 1974; Zoli and Congiu, 2024). Theories such as Planned Behavior expanded on psychological antecedents of consumer preferences, suggesting that behavior is driven by behavioral intentions, which are determined by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 1991). However, these theories still viewed decisions as a product of conscious deliberation, while others such as the norm-activation model (NAM) considered the power of “irrational” aspects including morals, emotions, and habits (Jackson, 2005). Finally, integrative theories of consumer behavior described both internal and external aspects that affect decisions. Kollmuss and Agyeman (2002) address the complexity of the attitude-behavior gap, where individuals with positive attitudes toward pro-environmental behaviors often do not act on them. They highlight key factors that can drive or hinder pro-environmental behaviors: demographics, internal factors (motivation, environmental knowledge, and awareness, values, attitudes, emotions, locus of control, responsibilities, and priorities), and external factors (institutional, economic, social, and cultural). Based on an integrative approach to support environmentally sustainable behaviors, we consider demographics, attitudes, and physical infrastructures within the methodological framework (see section 3).

2.2.2. Internal factors related to sharing behavior

The SE literature has widely addressed user motivations, attitudes, and barriers.

Generally, economic benefits like cost savings and extra income are primary motivations for sharing. Users are also driven by convenience

rather than altruism (Bardhi and Eckhardt, 2012; Böcker and Meelen, 2017; Gullstrand Edbring et al., 2016). However, social and environmental motivations also exist, as participants seek community connections, new experiences, and reduced environmental impacts (Böcker and Meelen, 2017). Interestingly, environmental motivations alone do not drive participation in the SE without positive attitudes toward sharing (Hamari et al., 2016).

Motivations also depend on demographic characteristics and product types. For example, younger individuals value economic, practical, and environmental benefits more than older individuals, who may be more socially motivated; higher education may correlate with economic motivations, and higher-income groups may be less socially driven to participate (Böcker and Meelen, 2017; Ertz et al., 2017; Jelinkova et al., 2021). Similarly, sustainability, social contact, economy, and fun may be more important in product sharing compared to convenience in accommodation and mobility sharing (Kim and Jin, 2020). Nonetheless, cultural and contextual factors may affect these tendencies (Hansmann and Binder, 2023).

Attitudes toward sharing also vary by sharing activity, product type, and socio-demographic characteristics (Eckhardt et al., 2019; Jiménez Encarnación et al., 2024). For example, Kim and Jin (2020) stated that sharing tangible products is tied to greater control and psychological ownership, and Gullstrand Edbring et al. (2016) found that consumers generally favor second-hand and short-term renting over other sharing forms, as well as sharing products made from hard materials (e.g., tables) rather than soft ones. Younger, higher-income, and more educated individuals generally exhibit greater acceptance of sharing activities (Böcker and Meelen, 2017).

Barriers to adopting sharing activities include concerns about hygiene, product quality, and lack of trust (Eckhardt et al., 2019; Gullstrand Edbring et al., 2016). Hazée et al. (2020) outline functional barriers (e.g., complexity of sharing and potential risks) and psychological barriers (e.g., ingrained habits and concerns about sharing). Consumers are also challenged by the expected effort in P2P sharing (Laurenti and Acuña, 2020).

In the methodological framework, we link demographics to consumption and sharing attitudes and frame the lack of sharing supply as a barrier to sharing.

2.3. Consumption and sharing from a geospatial perspective

We present the state-of-the-art for consumption and sharing individually, as this approach is more common in the literature. Additionally, we introduce urban morphology studies, which are used in the framework to examine geospatial characteristics.

2.3.1. Consumption

Quantitative studies on household consumption have become crucial in guiding a transition toward more sustainable patterns (Shittu, 2020). Especially, studies focusing on sub-national scales are useful to identify strategies suited to local sustainability goals (Lavers Westin et al., 2020). In the field of urban metabolism (UM), top-down models to investigate national household consumption include Input-Output (IO) and Material Flow Accounting (MFA). Higher levels of spatial disaggregation (i.e., regional, municipal, etc.) have also been seen, for example, in multi-regional input-output (MRIO) studies at an urban scale (Hertwich and Peters, 2009; Lenzen and Peters, 2010), IO combined with household budget survey (HBS) data (Ala-Mantila et al., 2017; Jones and Kammen, 2014); Economy-Wide Material Flow Accounting (EW-MFA) at a regional scale (Di Donato et al., 2015), and extrapolations from national-level data to municipality level (Lavers Westin et al., 2020; Roibás et al., 2017). Amongst these, Whetstone et al. (2020) developed the Urban Material Flow Accounting (UMFA) method, which extrapolates HBS data to the neighborhood level based on household archetypes (see section 3.2). Other approaches based on extrapolation to the household/individual level are presented by Druckman and Jackson

(2009); Huysman et al. (2016) and Mieke et al. (2016).

While UM studies have helped to understand the resource consumption and subsequent environmental effects on various geographical scales, Wang et al. (2023) stress the importance of exploring the “internals” of these studies by visualizing results with geographic information systems (GIS). The use of GIS in spatial and urban planning enables a visually comprehensive analysis of different metrics (e.g., the impacts of household consumption) (Giaoutzi and Papadopoulou, 2021). However, Geremicca and Bilec (2024) found a lack of geographically oriented visualization in UM studies. Studies lacking geographic visualizations risk decontextualizing values from their actual locations and undermining the interrelations between the considered areas (Giaoutzi and Papadopoulou, 2021).

2.3.2. Sharing

A geospatial approach in the SE field often goes no further than considering whether different types of locations (e.g., urban vs. rural areas) affect user interest and participation (see section 1). Other scholars, including Affolderbach and de Chardon (2021) and Thebault-Spieker et al. (2017), studied how the presence of SIs relates to the theoretical concepts of connectivity, proximity, and residential clustering. Approaches with high geospatial granularity (e.g., considering neighborhood characteristics or the exact location of initiatives) tend to focus on sharing mobility and space. For example, Di Marino et al. (2024) developed an index of “shareability” for mobility and space in two districts in Oslo, Norway, by analyzing spatio-functional features such as walkability, bikeability, street profiles, and social interaction in the districts. Mariotti et al. (2017) and Coll-Martínez and Méndez-Ortega (2023) investigated location patterns for co-working spaces (CWS) in Milan and Barcelona, respectively, comparing the CWS locations to neighborhood characteristics such as density, population composition, environment, and visibility of the locations. An approach by Du et al. (2019) explored the spatiotemporal usage patterns of shared bikes and related them to land-use variables, social-demographic variables, presence of other utilities, and cycling environment. There are few high-granularity studies of household products, including Behrend et al. (2019) and Wang and Wang (2019) who created models for optimizing the delivery of items to consumers in the SE. To our knowledge, no other scientific study has employed a methodological framework that compares the demand and supply of sharing household products and suggests interventions based on this.

2.4. Urban morphology

Urban Morphology could be used to study the SE with a high level of geospatial granularity. Urban morphology studies, particularly from the field of “space syntax”, have focused on characterizing the level of centrality and accessibility of a street network, showing that the centrality of a street positively associates with the concentration of commercial activities (e.g., so-called attractions) (Hillier, 1996; Hillier et al., 1993; Scoppa and Peponis, 2015); and the volumes of pedestrian flows (Hillier and Iida, 2005; Stavroulaki et al., 2019, 2024). Empirical findings suggest that street centrality creates the potential for increased pedestrian accessibility, a potential that attracts further development of pedestrian-oriented retail and services, which in turn attracts even more pedestrians in a multiplier effect (Hillier et al., 1993). Additionally, other spatial properties describing accessibility, such as attraction distance and reach (see section 3.3), have been shown to impact the concentration of activities (Özbil et al., 2011, 2015).

As such, urban morphology studies have been used to examine suitable locations for attractions, including spaces where consumption can occur (i.e., retail). For instance, Qanazi et al. (2024) conducted angular integration (i.e., a measure of centrality) and connectivity analyses on a range of facilities, including retail spaces, to identify which required better placement. Similarly, Valluzzi et al. (2024) conducted attraction reach (i.e., a measure of accessibility) and angular integration

analyses for different services. They found that these measures had a significant impact on the availability of services, and highlighted the role of proximity and walkability to essential services in supporting sustainable cities. Moreover, Adebayo et al. (2022) investigated the correlation between the location of retail spaces and the supply and demand for them. They concluded that, amongst other measures, angular integration could predict the demand for retail locations across 3 UK cities.

To the best of our knowledge, urban morphology analyses have not been employed to study the SE. We propose that space syntax analyses, such as centrality, and accessibility analyses, such as attraction distance and attraction reach, are well-suited for identifying potential locations for SIs. While we produce results from the three analyses; the method and results for attraction reach are only included in the Appendix.

3. Methodological framework

In this study, we propose a methodological framework that can be used to describe the current state of a city in terms of sharing and to suggest interventions. By combining information on neighborhoods with the highest levels of demand (i.e., consumption of shareable household products and attitudes that facilitate sustainable sharing), but where the corresponding supply may not be easily accessible (i.e., SI locations), we can identify areas where new SIs could contribute to sustainable sharing. Then, ideal locations are identified according to their relative centrality within the area. Our methodological framework utilizes readily available secondary data (see examples in Section 4.2) and draws upon the Urban Material Flow Accounting method (Whetstone et al., 2020), and the Place Syntax Tool (Stähle et al., 2005; Stavroulaki et al., 2023a), with the steps outlined in Fig. 1. In short, the methodological framework is applied as follows:

To assess the distribution of consumption throughout the city, national expenditure data are extrapolated to the neighborhood level using the extrapolation steps of the UMFA method (Whetstone et al., 2020) (section 3.2.). To assess the distribution of attitudes related to sustainable sharing, data from city-level user surveys are also extrapolated to the neighborhood level using an adaptation of the UMFA method (section 3.2). In our application of the framework, the attitudes considered are the “perception of owning too many products” and the “attitudes to different sharing activities”.

To assess the accessibility of physical mediated sharing throughout the city, spatial analyses (i.e., street network centrality, attraction

distance, and reach) are performed using data on the street network of a city, data of all buildings in the city (i.e., both residential and non-residential), and data on the location of mediated physical SIs in the city (section 3.3.).

Finally, the analysis of areas for SIs development is conducted through a visual comparison in GIS. We compare, neighborhood by neighborhood, the presence and accessibility of existing SIs with the highest tiers of product consumption and sharing attitudes. Highlighted locations are then assessed according to their street network centrality (section 3.4.).

3.1. Scope

The framework scope includes buildings, households, and SIs within a city. For the SIs, we focus on initiatives involving tangible and durable household products (clothes and shoes, children’s equipment, tools, furniture and decoration, hobby equipment, electronics, and kitchen equipment). Sharing activities considered are those that allow a reduction of consumption, thus spanning from remunerated or not, to permanent and temporary transactions (buying and selling second-hand, loaning to and from private individuals, renting from a SI, and reparation). In this study, the method is showcased for physical initiatives, including brick-and-mortar shops, unmanned libraries and sharing boxes. Accessibility to SIs is measured through pedestrian and cycling movement. While this excludes other ways to engage in sustainable sharing (e.g., postal-based online P2B2P sharing), the results related to the physical built environment can contribute to spatial planning toward sustainability.

3.2. Extrapolating expenditure and user attitudes to neighborhood level

The UMFA was developed by Whetstone et al. (2020) as a step toward performing neighborhood-scale UM studies. In the framework, the UMFA is used to extrapolate the variables of product consumption (national level), perception of owning too much, and attitude toward sharing activities (city level), to the neighborhood level. We adjust the UMFA by excluding the transformation of expenditure data into physical units (e.g., kg) but maintain the steps to calculate average values per population group and extrapolation to the neighborhood level.

For consumption, expenditure data (in monetary units) are extrapolated using the original population groups in Whetstone et al. (2020), based on dwelling type, income levels, and presence of children in the

Fig. 1. Methodological framework for comparing supply and demand of sharing, and for suggesting locations for interventions. The framework is showcased for mediated physical sharing at pedestrian and biking distances. The figure illustrates the steps undertaken throughout the framework, the methods utilized, and the guiding questions to produce the results.

household (see Table 1). The perception of owning too much is extrapolated using the same population groups as for consumption, and attitudes toward sharing activities (in percentages per area) are extrapolated by creating population groups based on age, gender, education level, and household composition (Jiménez Encarnación et al., 2024) (see Table 1). Further details on the UMFA method can be seen in Appendix 3.

3.3. Spatial analyses

Relevant spatial analyses that describe how urban form affects how people use the built environment are attraction distance (i.e., proximity), and street network centrality (i.e., angular integration). These analyses can be performed using the Place Syntax Tool, an open-source plugin for the open-source GIS platform QGIS (Ståhle et al., 2005; Stavroulaki et al., 2023a). See the equations for all analyses in Appendix 3.

3.3.1. Attraction distance

Attraction analyses combine street network analysis with the distribution of attractions to capture how resources are geospatially distributed and whether they are easily accessible. “Attraction distance” measures the distance from given origin points to the nearest attraction (Stavroulaki et al., 2023b). Note that this analysis measures walking distance, not straight-line distance (as the crows fly). This is important because an attraction might appear close in straight-line distance, but due to disrupted or sparse street networks or due to pedestrian barriers (e.g., highways, railway tracks), the walking distance may be significantly longer.

In the framework, we use the attraction distance analysis to calculate the pedestrian and biking distance from all buildings in the city (i.e., origins) to the nearest SI in a data sample (i.e., destination). To reflect user preferences and conventional travel behavior (Öhrwall, 2021), all buildings are used as origins, rather than just selecting residential buildings. This implies that accessibility is assessed from wherever users are located (e.g., at work, in leisure spaces, at home). The analyses are

Table 1

Population groups used to extrapolate expenditures and user attitudes to the neighborhood level. Note that the groups are based on relevant demographic characteristics for the case city and may vary when applied to other contexts.

Variable	Population characteristics used for extrapolation	Population groups
Product consumption (For the 7 product groups)	Disposable household income (Low – L, Medium – M, High – H)	12 groups (L-H-K, M-H-K, H-H-K, etc.) <i>Example: L-H-K means households with low disposable income (L), living in a house (H), and with children (K)</i>
Perception of owning too much (For the 7 product groups)	Dwelling type (House – H, Apartment – A) Presence of children in the household (Kids – K, No Kids – NK)	
Attitude toward sharing activities (For 5 out of 6 sharing activities- for buying and selling second-hand, see below)	Age (Below 65 – <65, 65 and above – >65) Gender (Man – M, Woman – W) Education level (Post-secondary education – P, Below post-secondary education – B)	8 groups (>65-M-P, >65-W-P, etc.) <i>Example: >65-M-P means individuals who are above 65 years of age (>65), identify as a man (M), and have post-secondary education (P)</i>
Attitude toward sharing activities (For buying and selling second-hand)	Age (Below 65 – <65, 65 and above – >65) Gender (Man – M, Woman – W) Education level (Post-secondary education – P, Below post-secondary education – B) Number of adults (1 adult – S, 2 adults – C, Other – O)	24 groups (>65-M-P-S, >65-M-P-C, >65-M-P-O, etc.) <i>Example: >65-M-P-S means individuals who are above 65 years of age (>65), identify as a man (M), have post-secondary education (H), and live alone (S).</i>

performed for each product and sharing activity using the non-motorized street network, the building locations, and the SI locations. No distance constraints are used in the analyses, to ascertain accessibility throughout the city irrespective of whether the resulting distances are deemed walkable.

3.3.2. Angular integration

To analyze street network centrality, we employ the space syntax measure “angular integration” (Hillier and Iida, 2005). This measure analyzes the street network configuration to calculate how close or distant, how integrated or segregated a location is in relation to other locations. While it is a variation of the well-used measure “closeness centrality”, angular integration uses angular distance rather than only metric or topological distance. Angular distance (i.e., total degrees turned from origin to destination) has been shown to correspond better to how pedestrians navigate, since people tend to choose the straightest routes that minimize both the metric and the perceived distance created by turns and changes of direction (Dalton, 2003; Hillier and Iida, 2005). Since angular integration positively associates with rates of pedestrian movement, social encounters, and concentration of retail activities (Hillier and Iida, 2005; Stavroulaki et al., 2019), it could help infer which locations are ideal for attracting more casual customers for attractions.

In the framework, the angular integration analysis is performed using the non-motorized street network dataset of a city and a 2 km walking distance radius. The 2 km radius accounts for street centrality at the neighborhood level, known as “local integration” (Stavroulaki et al., 2019), and highlights local centers and main streets where other services and attractions are likely located. All networks within a city are analyzed, as well as those outside the city borders within a 5 km buffer zone in all directions. This prevents distortions in the measurements along the city borders (i.e., “edge effect”) (Gil, 2017).

3.4. Identifying areas with opportunities

Results for each of the previously described variables are visualized in QGIS. To facilitate comparison across different variable units (e.g., monetary, kilometers, percentages), consumption, attitudes, and angular integration results are visualized using the Jenks natural breaks classification method with 7 categories (low to high). This cartography method optimizes data clustering by reducing the variance within categories and maximizing the variance between categories (Jenks, 1967). Conversely, attraction distances are visualized along 4 categories dictated by distance ranges preferred for different transportation modes (e.g., below 1 km for walking, between 1 and 3 km for biking, etc.) (Gehl, 2010).

Next, each of the “demand” variable visualizations (i.e., consumption, owning much, attitudes to sharing) are overlaid with their respective attraction distance analyses per product and activity (accessibility of “supply”). In our application of the framework, neighborhoods with unfulfilled sharing “demand” are defined as those with the highest tiers of demand but where the pedestrian accessibility (i.e., attraction distance) from buildings to SIs is greater than 3 km. Therefore, the comparison answers questions such as “Do areas with the highest consumption of clothes have SIs at an appropriate walking distance?”

Finally, neighborhoods with partially or entirely unfulfilled demands are overlaid with the street network’s local angular integration analyses. This allows identifying central locations where the street network configuration favors the placement of new, relevant SIs.

4. Application of the framework to the case city

This section provides details about the case city and the data sources used to apply the methodological framework. We then demonstrate the types of results that can be obtained by applying each step of the framework and reflect on how the real-life conditions of the case city

Table 2
Summary of data sources, their characteristics, and data processing for each method step.

Method step	Data source	Characteristics	Data processing
Consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Swedish Household Budget Survey (HBS) for 2021 (Statistics Sweden, 2024) 	<p>Sample: 8,097 households</p> <p>Scale: National level</p> <p>Households register their expenses in purchases (positive values) and earnings from sales (negative values) within different product categories.</p>	We only use positive values, assuming that expenditures represent product consumption. Thirty-eight product categories from the HBS were aggregated into the 7 product groups considered in the study (See Appendix 2).
User attitudes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questionnaire survey conducted by the Sharing Cities Gothenburg (SCG) project in 2021 (Institutet för kvalitetsindikatorer AB, 2021; Sharing Cities Sweden, 2021) 	<p>Sample: 961 individuals</p> <p>The survey had a stratified probability sampling approach, obtaining a 34.3 % response rate. All details about the survey are presented by Jiménez Encarnación et al. (2024) and in the survey's technical report (Institutet för kvalitetsindikatorer AB, 2021).</p> <p>Scale: City level</p> <p>The survey focused on attitudes and behaviors regarding the SE in Gothenburg.</p>	<p>Responses underwent post-stratification to correct over- or under-representation of the population's demographic makeup.</p> <p>We analyzed the variables "perception of owning too many products" (for each of the 7 product groups considered) and "attitude to sharing activities" (for each of the 6 sharing activities considered).</p> <p>To avoid social desirability bias, only responses that marked that they were "very positive" toward sharing activities were considered, as in Jiménez Encarnación et al. (2024).</p> <p>Although the activity "loaning from an SI" was not compatible across all sources, it was included due to its analytical relevance (see section 4.3.2). On the contrary, the activity "Renting to and from private individuals" was excluded due to lack of compatibility with other sources and lack of analytical relevance.</p> <p>We extrapolate the HBS and SCG data to the neighborhood level by using household and individual statistics.</p> <p>The statistics on number of households per neighborhood and on median incomes were used to extrapolate consumption, while the statistics on number of individuals per neighborhood were used to extrapolate attitudes.</p> <p>Our analysis of Gothenburg focuses on the city's administrative boundaries, thus excluding Gothenburg's greater metropolitan area. We analyzed 94 neighborhoods out of 96 throughout Gothenburg. Neighborhoods Högsbo and Arendal were excluded due to their low population and lack of statistics.</p> <p>Data for Gothenburg's CO₂ emissions for clothes, shoes, and hobby equipment was obtained from the Stockholm Environmental Institute (2024). Data protected under the Creative Commons license CC BY-NC-ND 4.0. © Stockholm Environmental Institute 2022.</p> <p>Individual responses for each variable were aggregated to the district level, according to their demographic characteristics. See details in Appendix 3.</p>
Extrapolating data to the neighborhood level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Statistics on number of households according to household composition, type of dwelling and neighborhood for 2017 Median household income per household composition at a national and city level, for 2017 and 2021 Median household income according to household composition and type of dwelling for 2017 at neighborhood level Statistics on number of individuals per neighborhood according to gender, age, educational level, and household composition for 2021 (Göteborgs Stad Statistik och Analys, 2022; Statistics Sweden, 2022a) 	<p>Scale: National, city, and neighborhood level</p>	<p>We extrapolate the HBS and SCG data to the neighborhood level by using household and individual statistics.</p> <p>The statistics on number of households per neighborhood and on median incomes were used to extrapolate consumption, while the statistics on number of individuals per neighborhood were used to extrapolate attitudes.</p> <p>Our analysis of Gothenburg focuses on the city's administrative boundaries, thus excluding Gothenburg's greater metropolitan area. We analyzed 94 neighborhoods out of 96 throughout Gothenburg. Neighborhoods Högsbo and Arendal were excluded due to their low population and lack of statistics.</p> <p>Data for Gothenburg's CO₂ emissions for clothes, shoes, and hobby equipment was obtained from the Stockholm Environmental Institute (2024). Data protected under the Creative Commons license CC BY-NC-ND 4.0. © Stockholm Environmental Institute 2022.</p> <p>Individual responses for each variable were aggregated to the district level, according to their demographic characteristics. See details in Appendix 3.</p>
Verification of consumption extrapolations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consumption Compass model (Axelsson et al., 2022) 	<p>Scale: Postcode level</p> <p>Online tool that visualizes consumption-based CO₂ emissions throughout Sweden.</p>	<p>Data for Gothenburg's CO₂ emissions for clothes, shoes, and hobby equipment was obtained from the Stockholm Environmental Institute (2024). Data protected under the Creative Commons license CC BY-NC-ND 4.0. © Stockholm Environmental Institute 2022.</p> <p>Individual responses for each variable were aggregated to the district level, according to their demographic characteristics. See details in Appendix 3.</p>
Verification of attitudes' extrapolations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questionnaire survey conducted by the Sharing Cities Gothenburg (SCG) project in 2021 (Institutet för kvalitetsindikatorer AB, 2021; Sharing Cities Sweden, 2021) 	<p>Scale: District level</p>	<p>Individual responses for each variable were aggregated to the district level, according to their demographic characteristics. See details in Appendix 3.</p>
Sharing initiatives in Gothenburg	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart Map Gothenburg (Smarta Kartan, 2023b) 	<p>Number of initiatives: 335</p> <p>Sampling: Initiatives apply for inclusion, and Kollaborativ Ekonomi (2023), the organization managing the Smart Map, filters and adds applications based on its criteria. The inclusion criteria were co-created with Gothenburg Municipality, focusing on environmental and social sustainability.</p> <p>Scope: The Smart Map prioritizes initiatives promoting sustainable consumption and activities such as renting, sharing, exchanging, borrowing, giving/receiving, do-it-yourself repairing, buying, and selling second-hand. The scope of the map therefore overlaps with our concept of sustainable sharing.</p>	<p>The location and characteristics of SIs were extracted from the Smart Map Gothenburg under the Open Database License v1.0. Since this data source does not follow a probability sampling, the percentual coverage of the Smart Map is not available. Therefore, the data from the Smart Map were used as a general indication of supply. Nonetheless, this is to our knowledge the largest collection of SIs in Gothenburg.</p> <p>The 335 initiatives in the sample were categorized by product offered and by sharing activity and reduced to a total of 219 corresponding to the study's 7 product groups and 6 sharing activities. Appendix 2 shows the number of initiatives corresponding to each categorization.</p> <p>No analyses were performed for the product category called "things", and the sharing activity "free exchanges", due to lack of compatibility with the other data sources.</p> <p>Space, mobility, and food sharing were excluded.</p>

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Method step	Data source	Characteristics	Data processing
Spatial analyses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-motorized street network of Gothenburg (open-access, see Stavroulaki et al. (2020)) • Building polygons in Gothenburg (Berghauser Pont et al., 2018) 	<p>Scope: The non-motorized network excludes all roads that prohibit walking and cycling (e.g. motorways, high-speed tunnels) and includes all streets and paths accessible for pedestrians and cycling, even if said paths are shared with vehicles. The building polygons include all buildings in Gothenburg, irrespective of use.</p>	Geospatial datasets were utilized to analyze street network centrality, and attraction distance (i.e. proximity). Attraction reach was also analyzed between SIs and buildings, and between SIs and public transport stations, see Appendix 4, Fig. 4V and Fig. 4W for results. All datasets were provided by the Spatial Morphology Group (2024) at Chalmers University of Technology.
Verification of street network local integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geospatial data on the local markets in Gothenburg (Bobkova et al., 2019) 	<p>Scale: City level</p> <p>Scope: Bakery, beauty shop, beverages, bicycle shop, book shop, butcher, car dealership, car rental, car sharing, car wash, chemist, clothes, computer shop, convenience, department store, do-it-yourself, florist, furniture shop, garden center, gift shop, greengrocer, hairdresser, jeweler, kiosk, laundry, mall, mobile phone shop, newsagent, optician, outdoor shop, shoe shop, sports shop, stationary, supermarket, toy shop, travel agent, video shop, food and drinks, Bar, café, fast food, food court, pub, restaurant.</p>	Dataset provided by the Spatial Morphology Group (2024) at Chalmers University of Technology.

compare to these results. Finally, we conduct a verification of the results. Note that the case results are based on non-comprehensive secondary data and would require additional data sources to ensure representativeness (see data limitations in section 5.4.1).

4.1. Case city: Gothenburg, Sweden

Gothenburg, the second-largest city in Sweden, is located on the west coast and houses approximately 590,000 people, with a median income of around 330,000 Swedish crowns/year (€29,000/year) ([Göteborgs Stad Statistik och Analys, 2022](#)). The city is divided into three functional areas: the inner-, middle-, and outer city, each with distinct characteristics in terms of population density, dwelling types, and services. The middle city is further divided into four subareas - Central Hisingen, Angered, East middle city and Southwest middle city ([Göteborgs Stad, 2022](#)). Despite high consumption levels, Gothenburg has plans to reduce CO₂ impacts and household waste by shifting consumption patterns ([Göteborg Stad, 2021](#); [Göteborgs Stad, 2020](#)). Further, Gothenburg Municipality fosters the SE by co-producing tools like the Smart Map, a platform that maps SIs in the city ([Kollaborativ Ekonomi, 2023](#); [Sharing Cities Alliance, 2018](#)). As for mobility, the city's Transport Plan aims to facilitate day-to-day life by densifying activities and supporting pedestrian and cycle transport within the local environment ([City of Gothenburg, 2014](#)). [Appendix 1](#) provides additional details on Gothenburg's population, administrative divisions, and pedestrian accessibility.

4.2. Data sources

In applying the framework, we utilize various data sources for the consumption estimation, assessment of user attitudes, extrapolations to the neighborhood level, identification of SIs in the city, spatial analyses, and verification of the results. The specifics of each data source and the corresponding data processing steps are detailed in [Table 2](#).

4.3. Spatial consumption and sharing patterns in the city

Based on the data from the case study, here we illustrate how the methodological framework can help identify spatial patterns regarding household consumption and sharing attitudes (demand), and the presence of SIs (supply). [Appendix 4](#) presents all numerical results obtained from applying the framework.

4.3.1. Sustainable sharing demand

The application of the framework showed subtle differences between the product consumption patterns. Products like furniture displayed higher-consumption neighborhoods scattered throughout the inner and outer city. Higher consumption was also found for hobby, kitchen and children's equipment, clothes, and electronics in the middle city. The lack of similar studies makes it difficult to verify why these patterns were so similar, but our comparison with an additional data source (section 4.6.) indicates a good approximation for consumption in key areas such as Nored, Kärra, Bergum, and Billdal; all neighborhoods in the outer city.

Conversely, tools showed a clearer concentration of higher-consumption neighborhoods towards the outer city ([Fig. 2 – Top row](#)). This might be explained by external factors related to the higher number of single-family houses in the outer city ([Göteborgs Stad, 2022](#)), as houses require more privately conducted reparations than rented apartments. A higher presence of gardens in houses might also increase interest in gardening tools ([Hunka and Habibi, 2023](#); [Jiménez Encarnación et al., 2024](#)).

More distinct spatial patterns were seen for “owning too much” and for “positive attitudes toward sharing”. Owning too many clothes predominantly occurred in the inner city, while hobby and kitchen equipment had high ownership in the north and south parts of the city, respectively. In the middle city, the highest perception of ownership occurred for electronics and furniture, while for tools and children's equipment, the highest results were seen in the outer city ([Fig. 2 – Middle row](#)). The higher ownership of tools in the outer city might be explained by the also higher consumption in the outer city. Tools have longer lifespans and are bought relatively seldom ([Curtis and Lehner, 2019](#)), so a high annual consumption could indicate a longstanding pattern of frequent tool purchases and accumulation in these neighborhoods. High ownership of children's equipment in the outer city is related to the higher presence of children-families ([Göteborgs Stad, 2022](#)).

The most positive attitudes toward loaning to and from private individuals and renting from SIs, were seen in the inner and middle city. The positive attitudes toward these temporary exchanges coincide with external factors such as a higher SI and population density in these areas ([Göteborgs Stad, 2022](#)), which would make it more practical to return items and find peers to share with ([Affolderbach and de Chardon, 2021](#)). Positive attitudes toward buying and selling second-hand were

prevalent in the south of the city, while repair attitudes are more prominent towards the city's edges, including the middle and outer city (Fig. 2 – Bottom row). The preference for buying and selling second-hand in the outer city areas coincides with high consumption in these areas, which could increase households' ability to provide their assets and free up their stock.

4.3.2. Physical mediated sharing supply

The application of the method indicated clear patterns in the distribution of SIs. SIs offering kitchen and children's equipment, furniture, tools, and clothes were primarily aggregated in the inner and middle city, with increasing SI density in the inner city. Electronics and hobby equipment were distributed uniformly throughout the city, although not always displaying a high SI density in the outer city (Fig. 3 - Top). Reasonably, the SI supply and accessibility in the inner and middle city appeared sufficient, as these more central and integrated locations have the most economic activity and suitable street networks that facilitates pedestrian and bike access (Göteborgs Stad, 2022). The even spread of hobby equipment and electronics sharing beyond these areas can be explained by our product group characterization. Books, categorized as hobby equipment, and printers, categorized as electronics, are available in the well-distributed city libraries, which are generally found in areas with high integration and pedestrian accessibility.

Regarding sharing activities, most initiatives concentrated in the inner and middle city, except for "Loan from SI" showing a broader geographical spread (Fig. 3 - Bottom). However, stark differences were seen regarding the density according to the activity. Notably, the lower availability of loaning to and from private individuals, and selling second-hand, can be explained by our study scope, as these activities may be more common on digital sharing platforms such as *Tradera* (2024) and *Hygglo* (2023) than in physical SIs.

4.4. Overlaying accessibility of supply and demand

This section exemplifies how to overlay the accessibility of supply and demand, by analyzing how the demands for sustainable sharing (i.e., consumption, owning too much, and positive attitudes toward sharing) overlap with the accessibility of SI supply (i.e., attraction distances). All figures from these analyses can be seen in [Appendix 4](#).

Starting from a "consumption" perspective, we previously saw the highest values scattered through the city, except for tools. For the accessibility of supply, pedestrian distances for all products except kitchen equipment were regularly below 3 km within the middle and inner city, and in the outer city for hobby equipment and electronics. Based on this analysis, the two products with the most fulfilled demands were electronics ([Appendix 4 – Fig. 4.G.](#)) and hobby equipment ([Fig. 4 – Top left](#)). The latter is provided in the city libraries, which exhibit the "Loan from SI" activity and are well-distributed in the city ([Fig. 4 – Bottom right](#)). For both products, some lower accessibility arose in larger neighborhoods such as Nolered and Billdal (see location in [Appendix 1 – Fig.1.B.](#)), with attraction distances sometimes exceeding 5 km. Furniture, children's equipment, and clothes displayed generally fulfilled demands in the inner city with pedestrian distances below 0.5 km; though surpassing 5 km in the outer city. The clothes results resemble the study of [Herold and Prokop \(2023\)](#), where more urban contexts were associated with a higher density of clothes SIs (2023). Tools, with the highest consumption values in the outer city, exhibited attraction distances often surpassing 3 km, indicative of an unfulfilled demand ([Fig. 4 – Top row](#)).

Considering the attitudes, there were varied patterns for "owning too much" depending on the product. When comparing this to supply accessibility, the clothes demand appeared fulfilled, with buildings within the high-ownership neighborhoods typically within 1 km of an SI. Similar trends were observed for electronics and furniture, with exceptions in some middle-city neighborhoods where distances ascended to 3 km. For tools, and hobby, children, and kitchen equipment, the demand

overlapped poorly with the SI supply accessibility, as most buildings within the high-ownership neighborhoods were over 3–5 km distance to the nearest initiative ([Fig. 4 – Middle row](#)).

Finally, the "positive attitudes toward sharing activities" also displayed varying patterns, and the accessibility of supply varied greatly since some activities had very few SIs (see [Appendix 2 – Table 2C.](#)). The "Loan from SI" activity was the most spread throughout the city, but the SCG survey does not account for the demand. Otherwise, we observed partially to completely unfulfilled demands for all remaining activities, with distances outside the inner city often exceeding 3 km. The most fulfilled demand was seen for "renting from SIs" ([Fig. 4 – Bottom left](#)), with typical attraction distances of 0.5–3 km in the higher-demand inner-city neighborhoods. Renting is also a more established sharing form, drawing on internal factors such as trust and familiarity. Conversely, accessibility to SIs offering activities like "loaning to and from private individuals" and "selling and buying second-hand" rarely showed distances below 1 km, even in high-demand inner-city neighborhoods. Reparation, with high demands in the outer city, generally had pedestrian distances to SIs exceeding 5 km ([Fig. 4 – Bottom row](#)). It is noteworthy that the demand for reparation appears unfulfilled in these areas, as reparation would bypass barriers that are common for other activities (e.g., in P2B2P exchanges in lower population areas, it might be challenging to coordinate supply and demand between peers).

4.5. A city perspective on sharing opportunities

In this section, we illustrate how to summarize the identified unfulfilled demands throughout the city and how to reflect on opportunities to address these demands.

4.5.1. Unfulfilled demands by city areas

[Fig. 5](#) shows a summary, per neighborhood, of sharing demands that were partially or completely unfulfilled by the available supply. Note that, as the method focuses on neighborhoods with the highest tiers of consumption and attitudes, the neighborhoods are prioritized for the corresponding product or mode independently of the actual demand value.

In the outer city, many unfulfilled demands were observed for sharing products, usually for tools and children's and hobby equipment. Kärra, Nolered, and Billdal had unfulfilled demands for five products or more. The lack of accessible supply is consistent with the generally lower amount of retail and services offered in the outer city ([Göteborgs Stad, 2022](#)), and relatively lower values of local integration reduce pedestrian accessibility to services that do exist in these areas (see [Appendix 4 – Fig.4V](#)). Since the demand was dictated by higher "consumption" or "owning too much" values, households in these areas likely access products outside the local context. The only relevant activities in the outer city were reparation and selling second-hand.

The application of the method showed important distinctions between middle-city divisions. There were many unfulfilled demands identified in the Southwest middle city, especially related to tools, and children, hobby, and kitchen equipment, and several sharing activities. The low supply may be related to the abundance of single-family houses and the geographical location toward the coast, making the area similar to the outer city.

Finally, the inner city and middle city areas besides Southwest generally had high accessibility to SIs in the high-demand areas, which could indicate that these areas have the right internal and external factors to engage in physically mediated sharing. The exceptions were kitchen equipment and furniture, and the "loaning to and from private individuals", "selling second-hand", and "renting from SIs" activities. The exception for kitchen equipment could be associated with how SIs are categorized in the Smart Map (i.e., the product tag "things" might include kitchen equipment, while we excluded this category due to lack of compatibility with other sources; see [Table 2](#)).

Fig. 2. A representative product or activity exemplifies the patterns observed in the demand variables. Top row: Consumption, Middle row: Owning too much, Bottom row: Positive attitudes toward activities. Left: patterns concentrating mostly in the inner city, Middle: patterns spreading toward the middle city, Right: patterns predominant in the outer city. The grey scale represents the result hierarchy, from highest (Black) to lowest (White) values. The inner city is delineated in pink, the middle city in orange, and outer city in purple. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. Typical patterns for the location of SIs within our study. Initiatives are marked in red. Top row: product patterns, Bottom row: activity patterns. Left: patterns heavily concentrated in the inner city with some presence in the middle city, Right: patterns with higher spread throughout the city. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

4.5.2. Opportunities to address demands

Previously, the overlapping of supply and demand indicated a need for broader supply of product sharing in the outer- and Southwest middle city, and for more diverse activities in the middle- and inner city.

The next step is to identify specific locations suitable for implementation of new SIs, by considering the local integration results of each highlighted city area. This is demonstrated in Fig. 6. Note that, due to limitations in the supply data, this section is an exemplification of how the

method results could look.

For neighborhoods in the Southwest middle city, the best opportunities were in the high-integration networks (marked in red). The highlighted neighborhoods in this area are the only ones in the entire city with a high network integration (see Appendix 4 – Fig. 4.V), but with low or no presence of SIs. Thus, the potential for economic activity associated with network integration could be utilized by SIs in these areas (Hillier and Iida, 2005; Stavroulaki et al., 2019). In the outer city neighborhoods, networks generally did not reach maximum levels of local integration. Therefore, for these neighborhoods, the best opportunities were on the streets with medium-high integration (marked in orange and yellow), which are relatively the most central streets within their local context. Due to its comparatively higher level of network integration, we also included the neighborhood Bergum as an opportunity.

The methodological framework suggests placing SIs on the most central streets in neighborhoods with unfulfilled demands. This would ensure pedestrian accessibility within the neighborhood and proximity to other non-residential activities like cafes and supermarkets, which are usually situated in locally central locations (Göteborgs Stad, 2022; Hillier, 1996; Scoppa and Peponis, 2015). It would also increase the exposure of SIs to people conducting their daily errands and possibly attract new users. Central locations also typically have better public transport access compared to the rest of the outer city, facilitating access to SIs for those outside pedestrian reach and possibly enhancing the functioning of SIs (Gregorowicz-Kipszak et al., 2024). In the case city, several of the highly integrated areas had city libraries, which already provide mediated physical sharing. Placement of SIs near, or in association with libraries, could promote sustainable product sharing within a well-established local service. The same concept should apply to the diversification of sharing activities in the inner and middle city, where high-integration networks are more abundant.

Figs. 5 and 6 can also be used to identify other areas that have unfulfilled demands for fewer products or activities. For example, the density of SI supply could be increased throughout the whole city (based on “attraction reach” results in Appendix 4), and an increased variety of initiatives for different products and activities in the inner city would improve users’ chances of finding initiatives that suit their needs (e.g., one existing initiative for furniture might not offer the exact type of furniture that users demand).

4.6. Verification steps

To assess the performance of the methodological framework in the case of Gothenburg, we conduct verifications regarding the consumption and attitude estimations, and the local integration results.

To our knowledge, there is no other estimation of product consumption at a neighborhood level for Gothenburg. Therefore, the results of the case were visually compared to GIS postcode-level data from the Consumption Compass model, indicating Gothenburg’s CO₂ emissions for the categories of clothes, shoes, and hobby equipment (Axelsson et al., 2022; Dawkins et al., 2024). Fig. 7 shows that the highest values for the two datasets are present in the west outer city, south outer city, inner city, and north outer city. Greater similarities are seen for the hobby equipment product group.

To extrapolate user attitudes, we needed to determine the most suitable population group categories for each variable. Since no other dataset describes sharing attitudes by neighborhood in Gothenburg, we verified the population groups by comparing the results to district-level data in the SCG dataset. The chosen models present 3%–20% cumulative error values compared to the district results. All details from the verification are presented in Appendix 3.

Finally, to verify the local integration results, these are overlapped with existing data on local markets in Gothenburg (Bobkova, 2019), including food and retail (Fig. 8). The overlap indicates a good correspondence between locations with medium to high local integration and

the presence of local markets. This implies that local integration values can be successfully used to infer locations with increased pedestrian activity and services.

No comprehensive data sources were found for SI supply and sharing demand fulfillment at the neighborhood level. Thus, it would be necessary to collect primary data to verify these variables.

5. Methodological framework discussion

Below, we discuss methodological advances of the framework, limitations, implications, and future work.

5.1. Methodological advances

In this study, we have explored the geospatial dimension of sharing household products. We achieve this by developing a methodological framework that models consumption and user attitudes at a neighborhood level, analyzes the accessibility of SI supply, and identifies central locations with potential for physical mediated SIs (e.g., shops, unmanned libraries and sharing boxes). Our method addresses previously identified needs to optimize the location of physical sharing (e.g., rental lockers, Martin et al., 2021). Other methodologies to support sustainable sharing have addressed the location of SIs qualitatively (Claudelin et al., 2022), or focused on optimizing transportation between consumers and providers, without suggesting methods to determine suitable locations (Behrend, 2020).

Our study contributes to the fields of industrial ecology and urban metabolism by developing neighborhood-level consumption estimations, and we make a novel contribution to the SE field by bringing concepts from spatial analysis disciplines. Additionally, our focus on tangible household products contributes to an underexplored area in the SE research field (Leung et al., 2019), in contrast to the commonly studied mobility and accommodation sharing.

The methodological value of our work lies in providing recommendations for the establishment of SIs, prioritizing specific products, activities, neighborhoods and locations; by combining information on demand, supply, and local street network centrality. The combination of these factors may increase interest in and exposure to SIs, making them viable in the future. The framework could be applicable in national and international contexts, particularly in places that collect HBS data (e.g., Lithuania and Switzerland, European Commission, 2023; Federal Statistical Office, 2022), that have performed sharing market research (e.g., Malmö and Karlstad in Sweden, Barkman & Wedberg, 2021; Malmö Innovationsarena, 2016), that collect data on SIs (e.g., Seoul and Berlin, Labaeye, 2017; Moon, 2017), and that have street network data (e.g., Stockholm, Amsterdam and London, Berghauser Pont et al., 2019b). In future applications, the choice of attitude variables and population groups can be adapted to the local contexts.

Besides application to other cities, future development of the method could entail the following:

- Refining the local estimations on product consumption.
- Refining the framework to consider the nuances of each product and sharing activity considered (e.g., large vs. small products, temporary vs. permanent activities).
- Studying sharing through other transportation modes, such as public transportation (PT) by using data on stations locations (see section 5.4.3.), and car transport by using motorized street network data (e.g., Berghauser Pont et al., 2019a), longer distances in the attraction analyses, and city-level angular integration.
- Studying online P2B2P sharing at the local scale. Here, data would be needed on the locations of both peer providers and consumers (available, for example, in the app Hygglo, 2023). Then, space syntax centrality analyses of the street network, including angular integration and betweenness centrality, could help identify locations with a higher chance of co-presence of consumers and providers.

(caption on next page)

Fig. 4. Typical patterns for the overlay of demand (neighborhood layer) and accessibility of supply (building layer) for sharing. The neighborhood color scale represents the result hierarchy, from highest (Black) to lowest values (White). The building layer color scale represents the distance to the nearest SI, from shortest (Red) to longest (Blue) distances

Left: patterns where the supply fulfilled most demand. Middle: patterns with partially fulfilled demands. Right: patterns with unfulfilled demands. Example: the map in the middle row left column shows the overlay for clothes. Neighborhoods in black indicate the highest percentages of owning too many clothes, while buildings in red indicate good pedestrian accessibility to SIs. Since these overlapped well, these were neighborhoods where clothes demand could be satisfied by the physical sharing initiatives supply. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Map indicating neighborhoods with a poor overlap of supply and demand of sharing, by products and activities. A poor overlap is indicated with “C” for consumption, “OM” for owning too much, and blue text for sharing activities. Red text indicates medium accessibility (accessible by bike, or neighborhoods with mixed accessibility). Observe that the neighborhoods Kärä, Nolered and Billdal had unfulfilled demands for five products or more. The inner city is represented in pink, middle city in orange, and outer city in purple. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 6. Map showing locations with higher levels of local street network integration and the most unfulfilled demands. These locations are ideal for establishing relevant SIs. Network integration is represented in a color scale from high (Red) to medium (Yellow) integration; excluding networks with medium-low integration. The image also shows an example of pedestrian accessibility from buildings to existing tool SIs (Red circles), from 3 km (Teal) to over 5 km (Blue) pedestrian distances, excluding buildings with shorter distances. Note the lack of tool SIs in the neighborhood Bergum. Example: The neighborhoods in the Southwest middle city have an unfulfilled demand for sharing tools. Street networks in red have good integration, so these areas would be ideal for placing new SIs, which would increase pedestrian accessibility from buildings (origins) to SIs (destinations). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

- Studying opportunities for social and economic sustainability by facilitating sharing in areas where inhabitants might be unable to afford products. This would imply modifying the method to focus on tiers with the lowest consumption.
- Studying the co-presence of SIs and local markets, to facilitate sharing through multi-purpose trips.
- Studying participation in sharing activities included within the HBS data, such as selling second-hand and repairing products.
- Refining the sustainability implications of the methodological framework by integrating product life cycle impact indicators within the supply and demand of shareable products.

5.2. Applicability of the methodological framework for practice, governance, and sustainability

By utilizing representative data on the supply and demand of SIs, our framework can inform governance and practice recommendations for establishing new SIs. In Gothenburg, for example, this would require a more comprehensive sampling of SIs and other sharing manifestations, and confirmation of the supply and demand through in-depth studies (e.g., qualitative data on product ownership; purchasing, sharing, and travelling behavior; and other internal factors that influence pro-environmental behavior).

After confirming supply and demand in key areas, the implementation of new SIs should be guided by quantitative results similar to those in [Appendix 4](#) (e.g., if 60 % of the population has very positive attitudes toward repairation and 40 % toward selling second-hand, more SIs

Fig. 7. Comparing the top tiers of CO₂ emissions in the Consumption Compass data (Axelsson et al., 2022) (horizontal lines) to the top tiers of consumption results in our data (vertical lines), for the product group of clothes and shoes (left) and hobby equipment (right). Each of the results has been visualized using a 7-category Jenks Algorithm. The meshed areas show where the results within the highest hierarchies coincide in both maps.

should be implemented for reparation), while qualitative insights could guide decisions on the most suitable type of physical infrastructure (e.g., attached to existing services as libraries, new brick-and mortar shops, sharing boxes). Local governments could facilitate these measures by providing infrastructural support (e.g., available spaces) for businesses and organizations to establish SIs in highlighted locations (Voytenko Palgan et al., 2021). With municipality-led SIs being rare, civil society and entrepreneurs play a key role in establishing the new SIs. These stakeholders could benefit from such results while contributing to increased interpersonal trust, social capital, and economic opportunities for their users (Hossain, 2020).

Besides providing social and economic benefits, the development of SIs based on our framework could contribute to environmental sustainability by addressing two significant issues: reducing consumption-based environmental impacts and minimizing transport-related impacts. Still, intensified use of SIs might have unintended consequences, including rebound effects and increased maintenance and cleaning impacts. To tackle these, extant research suggests raising awareness about rebounds, as even environmentally motivated users may not be aware of this phenomenon (Ottelin et al., 2020; Ribera Jemio et al., 2024). To reduce cleaning and maintenance impacts, SIs should use low-impact methods and choose nearby facilities (Amasawa et al., 2023; Johnson and Plepys, 2021; Kerdlap et al., 2021). SIs can also nudge sustainable behavior by encouraging long-term use of shared products, thus cutting down on transportation impacts (Johnson and Plepys, 2021).

Additionally, it must be considered that the methodological framework relies on a simplified conceptualization of sustainable sharing. Yet, Section 2.1. showed that the sustainability of sharing is nuanced, as the replacement rates, transportation, sharing infrastructure, and sharing activities interact in complex ways. Thus, the resulting recommendations should be informed by life cycle assessment case studies, as seen in Martin et al. (2021) and Zamani et al. (2017). It is essential that the

assessments of suggested interventions consider the sensitivity of transportation impacts depending on the sharing activity, and the potential impacts of physical infrastructure and operations of the SIs. It is also relevant to study several impact categories to understand the possibilities for burden shifting, and to confirm replacement rates and rebound effects post-implementation through environmentally extended input-output analyses (Junnilla et al., 2018) or survey-based numerical models (Claudelin et al., 2022).

5.3. Theoretical implications of promoting sharing behavior

From an intervention standpoint, our work aligns with the OECD's steps to promote sustainable consumption by suggesting improvements based on current conditions (Zoli and Congiu, 2024). However, we must consider whether external interventions can effectively encourage users to participate in sharing, particularly with the example of physical SIs. On the one hand, Claudelin et al. (2022) saw that the design and implementation of a library of things (LoT) in a Finnish rural area delivered environmental benefits due to the involvement of relevant stakeholders. On the other hand, a study on location planning in Gothenburg reported that services, besides food and healthcare, may fail in areas with specific socio-demographic characteristics and lower PT accessibility (Gregorowicz-Kipszak et al., 2024). Zoli and Congiu (2024) noted the scarce evidence of behavioral interventions for sharing household products, with mixed results depending on the type of nudges. These examples underscore the need for integrative interventions that address both internal and external factors, consider local contexts, and involve relevant stakeholders.

In this sense, our study makes a theoretical contribution by emphasizing the interplay of internal and external factors, while the SE literature has primarily used theoretical frameworks based on internal factors (Camacho-Otero et al., 2018). Inspired by Kollmuss and

Fig. 8. Verification of the street network local integration results. Network integration is represented in a color scale from high (Red) to medium (Yellow) integration, excluding networks with medium-low integration. Black dots represent local markets in Gothenburg (e.g., food and retail) based on the data from Bobkova et al. (2019). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Agyeman (2002), we consider demographics as a moderating factor for sustainable behavior, attitudes toward consumption and sharing activities as internal factors, and the accessibility of SIs as an external factor:

Demographic characteristics are used as a feature of the UMFA method, which has implications for the potential adoption of sharing habits (see section 2.2.2.). For example, most highlighted neighborhoods in the studied case had above-average disposable incomes. Higher incomes have been linked to positive sharing attitudes, which in turn may influence behavioral intentions and promote changed behavior (Ajzen, 1991; Böcker and Meelen, 2017). The demographic makeup of suggested areas can also inform the implementation of SIs. For instance, the highlighted areas in Gothenburg had a higher presence of elderly individuals. Older individuals may be more socially motivated to share, so SIs in similar areas should consider the role of social embeddedness for encouraging sustainable consumption habits (Jackson, 2005).

Reflecting on user attitudes, the perception of owning too much implies a negative attitude and may relate to consumer preferences (i.e., preferring a minimalist lifestyle), social norms (i.e., comparison with other's consumption), moral aspects (i.e., anti-consumerist values), or even environmental awareness (i.e., associating own consumption with undesirable impacts). These factors may also drive behavioral changes and prevent rebounds and non-replacement of products in sharing.

As for user behavior, high consumption has a two-fold effect. From one perspective, it can indicate a need or desire for specific products in the highlighted areas, which could theoretically be met by local sharing rather than purchasing. From another perspective, the current consumption probably occurs outside the local sphere through conventional

purchasing, a habit that results from the interplay of internal and external factors (Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002). Since external factors play a moderating role in pro-environmental habit changes (Jackson, 2005; Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002), the externally based intervention of placing SIs in highly accessible areas could facilitate changed behavior, given the existing interest in close proximity sharing (Öhrwall, 2021).

Continuing with external factors (i.e., sharing infrastructure), the relative ease of physical mediated sharing might address the complexity and effort associated with other sharing forms (Hazée et al., 2020; Laurenti and Acuña, 2020). While it is undeniable that online sharing and purchasing are rapidly growing (PostNord & HUI Research, 2024), over 84 % of purchases in Sweden are still made in physical stores, with more than 70 % of Gothenburg residents not engaging in digital temporary transactions (Hagberg et al., 2022; Institutet för kvalitetsindikatorer AB, 2021; Sharing Cities Sweden, 2021). Therefore, our example of physical sharing may cater to existing purchasing habits, whereas digital sharing might pose additional challenges in the shift toward sustainable consumption. This, however, means that groups who are more inclined to share digitally might not be reached through the establishment of physical SIs, and could need complementary interventions to support a holistic transition toward sustainable consumption.

Finally, we have showcased an application of the framework that suggests externally based interventions, but other interventions could be aimed at modifying internal factors. This includes improving knowledge of the SE, marketing of SIs, and behavioral nudges (Camacho-Otero

et al., 2018; Hazée et al., 2020; Öhrwall, 2021). Given the lack of relevant evidence, more research is needed on the implementation and effectiveness of both internal and external SE interventions, from a theoretically integrative perspective. Additional factors, such as local culture and norms, could be studied through models like NAM.

5.4. Limitations

5.4.1. Data sources

As the method relies on multiple data sources, the results will depend on the quality of these sources. For example, Gothenburg's data presented several limitations that affect the validity of the case results: On the demand side, the HBS collection methods for 2021 changed from previous years, affecting the reliability of the consumption statistics (Statistics Sweden, 2022b); and both the SCG and HBS surveys were conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic, making consumption patterns and sharing attitudes potentially irregular (Esposti et al., 2021; Holmberg, 2021). On the supply side, the Smart Map excludes private (e.g., sharing rooms in workplaces) and short-term initiatives (e.g., flea markets), which reduced the coverage of P2P SIs. Additionally, the Smart Map's criteria for sustainable consumption and social sustainability exclude other initiative types, resulting in a limited representation of supply in Gothenburg (e.g., well-established repair shops fall outside the "not well-known" criteria) (Smarta Kartan, 2023a). This means that additional studies are needed to confirm the results of the case (see section 4.6.).

Similarly, the results of the framework application may be affected by the compatibility between data sources. For example, using broad product and activity categorizations can lead to inconsistencies in the overlap between supply and demand. This is exemplified by the discussion on the accessibility of electronics SIs in Gothenburg, as well as the exclusion of the Smart Map product tag "things" (in 174 initiatives) and the activities "giving, receiving, and exchanging" (in 20 initiatives), absent in the other data sources. In the Gothenburg case, the product and activity categorizations were driven by the differing disaggregation levels between data sources, but with more detailed data, it should be possible to obtain a precise match between supply and demand. Similarly, the geographical delimitations used in the Gothenburg data were generally similar (i.e., the postcode delimitation used for the UMFA method verification, the neighborhood delimitations used in the results, and the city areas used to facilitate analysis), but did not always overlap exactly. Thus, results could be inflated if some areas have been aggregated within high-consumption neighborhoods. The issue relates to the "modifiable area unit problem", in which different results can be achieved depending on how an area is zoned (Buzzelli, 2020). Finally, data sources might refer to different years. In the Gothenburg case, some statistics were available for 2021, while others were from 2017.

5.4.2. Demand calculations

Generally, the framework is limited by the use of expenditures as a proxy for consumption, which does not account for price variations within the same product categories and might inflate consumption results in high-income areas. In future applications, this can be addressed by using consumption data measured in units. It would also be valuable to differentiate between product purchases and sales, as HBS data subtracts earnings directly from expenditures within the same product category, potentially underestimating expenses per household. The framework is also limited by our focus on the highest consumption/percentage tiers, which overlooks the variance in the numerical results. For instance, neighborhood-level clothing expenditures in Gothenburg varied much more than tool expenditures, so the interpretation of tool expenditures might be skewed (see Appendix 4). Conversely, the method's emphasis on extreme values (e.g., being "very positive" toward sharing activities rather than "positive") may be conservative in some cases, potentially leading to under-prioritization of specific products or activities.

5.4.3. Supply conceptualization

The framework is also limited by the scope used (i.e., physical mediated sharing), particularly for the supply. The showcase of the method relied on the available data sources, whereas the Smart Map data excludes popular SE manifestations such as informal P2P sharing and online P2B2P sharing (Acquier et al., 2017; Curtis and Lehner, 2019). On the one hand, our scope has several advantages. Secondary data on mediated activities is more accessible to decision-makers (e.g., Smart Map); while informal sharing is often absent from national statistics due to a lack of monetization (Ottelin et al., 2020). Furthermore, physical sharing can address several user motivations and barriers (section 5.3.), and increase sharing participation by attracting casual passersby. On the other hand, this means that the contributions to sustainable sharing from informal and online sharing are missing from the supply. Particularly, these sharing forms might also reduce environmental impacts by securing transfers directly between providers and consumers, thereby eliminating potential impacts from SIs' operations and physical infrastructure, and potentially minimizing the stock required to satisfy user demands (Behrend, 2020).

Additionally, we showcase supply accessibility through pedestrian and cycling distances to SIs, which limits the supply for sustainable sharing. Life-cycle assessments have shown that transport configurations that combine PT with walking or biking report lower global warming impacts than using PT alone, suggesting advantages to sharing through these modes (Johnson and Plepys, 2021; Martin et al., 2019). However, the advantages of cycling and biking configurations vs. PT alone are not evident for other impact categories (e.g., human carcinogenic potential, freshwater impacts). Additionally, the impacts of more intensive transportation modes might not be as important when conducting permanent sharing transactions. While our scope implies minimum transportation impacts, there are several ways to mitigate these impacts, both in physical and online sharing. These include increasing the physical network of SIs and local sharing lockers, but also accessing products through PT, sharing through postal services, or simply integrating sharing within multi-purpose trips.

In conclusion, physical mediated sharing at pedestrian and biking distances can contribute to sustainable sharing, but it is not the only pathway to achieve this goal. Therefore, the showcase of the methodological framework is limited when overlapping supply and demand, as the demand could be, or already might be, satisfied by other sharing modes for which we do not know the supply (e.g., informal sharing, online sharing, sharing through PT, post, or combined with other purposes). Additionally, the short distances implied can bias the "untapped areas" toward residential areas with high consumption values. Both issues can be addressed through future research by expanding to other sharing activities and transportation modes, as suggested in section 5.1. To illustrate a pathway for addressing this limitation, we briefly exemplify the potential of sharing by PT in Gothenburg (see Appendix 4 – Fig. 4.W. and Table 4.D.). In short, the analyses showed high pedestrian accessibility from PT stations to SIs in Gothenburg's inner city, and moderate accessibility elsewhere, assuming an 800 m walking distance. The highlighted locations were typically 40 min away from key inner-city SIs and required one mode change, which might deter users from sharing unless integrated with other trips. To fully understand the potential of sharing through PT, more detailed studies involving multi-modal accessibility would be needed (as in Lopes et al., 2023).

Finally, using geospatial analyses to measure demand fulfillment is limited, as it only focuses on the physical aspects of space and does not account for other social and functional aspects that may influence SI usage (Jguirim et al., 2014; Qanazi et al., 2024). Our study partially addresses this by including internal factors (e.g., attitudes) as a representation of demand, but might be expanded by including additional measures mentioned in section 2.3.2.

6. Conclusion

Our research integrated a geospatial dimension into the study of sustainable sharing, by developing a methodological framework to identify locations where sharing demand may not be met by accessible supply. The framework utilizes secondary data sources and involves estimating consumption amounts and user attitudes at the neighborhood level, characterizing the accessibility of sharing initiatives supply, and analyzing the centrality of the street networks to suggest ideal locations for new sharing initiatives. The steps are based on a modification of the UMFA method, and on the urban morphology analyses attraction distance and local angular integration, performed with the Place Syntax Tool.

The viability of the methodological framework is demonstrated through an application to the city of Gothenburg, Sweden, focusing on mediated physical sharing at walking and biking distances. The case exhibited consistent spatial patterns in the consumption and supply of SIs, whereas the attitude patterns showed larger variations. The results indicated a need for more varied product SIs in the outer city, diversification of sharing activities in the middle city, and further densification of SIs in the inner city, although primary data is needed to confirm existing supply and demand.

Our methodological framework can be applied within urban planning, governance, and entrepreneurship to develop new SIs that fit the local contexts. We make a novel contribution to the underexplored scientific field of household goods sharing by integrating household consumption estimations and spatial analysis methods. Additionally, we make a theoretical contribution to the field by employing an integrative approach, which takes positive internal factors for sharing as a departure point and suggests external interventions to facilitate the adoption of pro-environmental behavior.

Study limitations are related to the quality and compatibility of data sources, as well as the study's scope, which limits the coverage of the sustainable sharing supply. Future method development includes the refinement of product consumption estimations at a neighborhood level, adaptation of the framework to specific products and activities, further exploration of opportunities for sustainable sharing within online peer-to-peer activities and through car and public transportation, and application of the framework to the social and economic sustainability dimensions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Divia Jiménez Encarnación: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Liane Thuvander:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Ioanna Stavroulaki:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Emiline Elangovan:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Leonardo Rosado:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used OpenAI ChatGPT to improve the code for the consumption and attitudes modeling and Microsoft Copilot to improve the readability and language of the article. After using these tools, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2025.146237>.

Data availability

Data that is publicly available is cited in the article

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